

www.arseam.com
Impact Factor: 2.48

Cite this paper as : Akshai M Sukumar et. al. (2017). Automated Smart Room, International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research, Volume 4,(Issue 1, Jan-2017), pp 24–39. ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print),

AUTOMATED SMART ROOM

**Akshai M Sukumar, Christo C J, Jayakrishnan A P, Nijo S Thanjan, Midhun Varghese
Reshma K R**

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
IES College of Engineering, Chittilappilly, Thrissur.

Abstract:

Objective- Here we are putting forward a design and development of smart monitoring and controlling system for household electrical appliances in real time .Also, eliminating the unwanted losses of electrical energy by the household appliances.

Design/Methodology/Approach- This idea will use sensors, real time clock etc for controlling the electrical appliances. It optimizes energy without compromising the comfort of the users. Remote controlling is another option that is available. The system principally monitors electrical parameters of household appliances such as voltage and current and subsequently calculates the power consumed. The novelty of this system is the implementation of controlling mechanism of appliances in different ways the developed system is a low cost and flexible in operation and thus can save expense of consumers. There is also an option for controlling the system manually if needed.

Findings- Automated smart rooms has been proposed and its suitability has been demonstrated through simulated results and experimental validation.

Practical implications- Nowadays the energy is wasted by modern people as they don't care much about energy so they use it according to their comfort. We can implement this idea in hospitals, classrooms, local purposes etc.

Key words: Room automation, smart room,

1. INTRODUCTION

OVERVIEW

Room automation involves the control and automation of various features of a room. It includes lighting, fan, exhaust etc. Nowadays the energy is wasted by modern people as they don't care much about energy so they use it according to their comfort. We must remember that energy is the most important aspect in every one's life, we should consider saving it. For this we can use the idea of automation

Automation of rooms helps in optimizing energy consumption and easy usage of room operations. It optimizes energy without compromise the comfort of the user GSM module is used for remote controlling of room features by the user itself. LDR and temperature sensors help in monitoring room light and temperature conditions respectively. This data is used for automatic control of light intensity and fan speed control. PIR sensor is included for human detection and Thief alerts. Alerts are sent to user's cell phone. Shades are automated according to time and human presence. The sound system which wakes up user in the morning also greets the user when entered to the

room. Exhaust fan is provided to improve air quality. If we are bored with automation, we can always switch to manual controlling mode. By initiating the automated smart rooms we can neglect the unwanted wastage of energy.

OBJECTIVE

- Optimizing energy consumption without compromising comfort
- Automation of room functions and remote controlling

2. STUDY OF AUTOMATION

Home automation or smart home (also known as domotics or domotica) is the residential extension of building automation and involves the control and automation of lighting, heating (such as smart thermostats), ventilation, air conditioning (HVAC), and security, as well as home appliances such as washer/dryers, ovens or refrigerators/freezers that use Wi-Fi for remote monitoring. Modern systems generally consist of switches and sensors connected to a central hub sometimes called a "gateway" from which the system is controlled with a user interface that is interacted either with a wall-mounted terminal, mobile phone software, tablet computer or a web interface, often but not always via internet cloud services.

While there are many competing vendors, there are very few world-wide accepted industry standards and the smart home space is heavily fragmented. Popular communications protocol for products include X10, Ethernet, RS-485, 6LoWPAN, Bluetooth LE (BLE), ZigBee and Z-Wave, or other proprietary protocols all of which are incompatible with each other. Manufacturers often prevent independent implementations by withholding documentation and by suing people. The home automation market was worth US\$5.77 billion in 2015, predicted to have a market value over US\$10 billion by the year 2020. The word "domotics" (and "domotica" when used as a verb) is a contraction of the Latin word for a home "domus" and the words/fields informatics, telematics and robotics. Early home automation began with labor-saving machines. Self-contained electric or gas powered home appliances became viable in the 1900s with the introduction of electric power distribution and led to the introduction of washing machines (1904), water heaters (1889), refrigerators, sewing machines, dishwashers, and clothes dryers.

In 1975, the first general purpose home automation network technology, X10, was developed. It is a communication protocol for electronic devices. It primarily uses electric power transmission wiring for signaling and control, where the signals involve brief radio frequency bursts of digital data, and remains the most widely available. By 1978, X10 products included a 16 channel command console, a lamp module, and an appliance module. Soon after came the wall switch module and the first X10 timer. By 2012, in the United States, according to ABI Research, 1.5 million home automation systems were installed.

There are three generations of home automation:

First generation: wireless technology with proxy server, e.g. Zigbee automation; Second generation: artificial intelligence controls electrical devices, e.g. amazon echo; Third generation: robot buddy "who" interacts with humans, e.g. Robot Rovieo, Roomba.

Applications and technologies: Heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC): it is possible to have remote control of all home energy monitors over the internet incorporating a simple and friendly user interface.

Lighting control system: Appliance control and integration with the smart grid and a smart meter, taking advantage, for instance, of high solar panel output in the middle of the day to run washing machines.

Security: a household security system integrated with a home automation system can provide additional services such as remote surveillance of security cameras over the Internet, or central locking of all perimeter doors and windows. Leak detection, smoke and CO detectors.

3. BASIC PRINCIPLE

THEORY

It is foreseen that service and personal care wireless mechatronic systems will become more and more ubiquitous at home in the near future and will be very useful in assistive healthcare particularly for the elderly and disabled people. Wireless mechatronic systems consist of numerous spatially distributed sensors with limited data collection and processing capability to monitor the environmental situation. Wireless sensor networks have become increasingly important because of their ability to monitor and manage situational information for various intelligent services. Due to those advantages, Wireless sensor network has been applied in many fields, such as military, industry, environmental monitoring, and healthcare.

The Wireless sensor networks are increasingly being used in the home for energy controlling services. Regular household appliances are monitored and controlled by Wireless sensor network installed in the home. New technologies include cutting-edge advancements in information technology, sensors, metering, transmission, distribution and electricity storage technology, as well as providing new information and flexibility to both consumers and providers of electricity. The ZigBee Alliance, wireless communication platform is presently examining Japan's new smart home wireless system implication by having a new initiative with Japan's Government that will evaluate use of the forthcoming ZigBee, Internet protocol specification, and the IEEE 802.15.4g standard to help Japan to create smart homes that improve energy management and efficiency

WORKING PRINCIPLE

A well-designed automation system can:

- improve passive solar heating and passive cooling through the control of blinds, awnings, windows, vents and fans
- control heaters and air conditioners so they are used only when and where they are needed and to achieve a desired temperature.

Before considering automation options, ensure that your home is designed to make the best use of solar energy and natural ventilation for passive heating and cooling (see Passive solar heating; Passive cooling).

Use thermostats or temperature sensors in different rooms to control heating and cooling. Appropriately placed, they, along with timers to control heating/cooling appliances, can significantly reduce energy use, even if automated systems are not used. The working principle of home/ room automation is mainly usage of wireless sensors and using it to control the features of home. For saving maximum energy we can use more of the resources that are available in the nature itself. In food services and pharmaceuticals, the tools are designed to be used in harsher environments, where the potential for corrosion is high due to being washed at high pressures and temperatures repeatedly to maintain strict hygiene standards. Servos are also used in in-line manufacturing, where high repetition yet precise work is necessary. The other main characteristic of cutting-edge home automation is remote monitoring and access. While a limited amount of one-way remote monitoring has been possible for some time, it's only since the rise in smartphones and tablets that we've had the ability to truly connect to our home networks while we're away. With the right home automation system, you can use any Internet-connected device to view and control the system itself and any attached devices.

Monitoring apps can provide a wealth of information about your home, from the status of the current moment to a detailed history of what has happened up to now. You can check your security system's status, whether the lights are on, whether the doors are locked, what the current temperature of your home is and much more. With cameras as part of your home automation system, you can even pull up real-time video feeds and literally see what's going on in your home while you're away.

Even simple notifications can be used to perform many important tasks. You can program your system to send you a text message or email whenever your security system registers a potential problem, from severe weather alerts to

motion detector warnings to fire alarms. You can also get notified for more mundane events, such as programming your "smart" front door lock to let you know when your child returns home from school.

The real hands-on control comes in when you start interacting with the home automation system from your remote app. In addition to arming and disarming your security system, you can reprogram the scheduling, lock and unlock doors, reset the thermostat and adjust the lights all from your phone, from anywhere in the world. As manufacturers are creating more and more "smart" devices and appliances all the time, the possibilities for home automation are virtually limitless. What kinds of things can be part of a home automation system? Ideally, anything that can be connected to a network can be automated and controlled remotely. In the real world (outside of research labs and the homes of the rich and famous), home automation most commonly connects simple binary devices. This includes "on and off" devices such as lights, power outlets and electronic locks, but also devices such as security sensors which have only two states, open and closed.

Where home automation becomes truly "smart" is in the Internet-enabled devices that attach to this network and control it. The classic control unit is the home computer, for which many of the earlier home automation systems were designed. Today's home automation systems are more likely to distribute programming and monitoring control between a dedicated device in the home, like the control panel of a security system, and a user-friendly app interface that can be accessed via an Internet-enabled PC, smartphone or tablet.

Manufacturers have produced a wide variety of "smart" devices, many of which are full of innovative features but few of which offer the kind of integration needed to be part of a complete home automation system. Much of the problem has been that each manufacturer has a different idea of how these devices should be connected and controlled. So while you may have a "smart" TV, washing machine, refrigerator, thermostat, coffee maker or any of the other Internet-ready household devices on the market, the end result is usually a separate control scheme for each device.

In the near future, home automation may be standardized to let us truly take advantage of all of these additional possibilities. For the time being, the home security providers that specialize in home automation have focused on the most critical and useful parts of a connected home. At a basic level, this means the doors and windows and environmental devices (thermostat, smoke detectors, temperature, humidity, fire and carbon dioxide sensors) that keep you safe and comfortable. For additional real-time security, convenience and control, home automation systems from security providers should also include options for video cameras. With the best systems, you'll also be able to include lights and individual electrical outlets into your home automation package. One clear advantage of home automation is the unmatched potential for energy savings, and therefore cost savings. Your thermostat is already "smart" in the sense that it uses a temperature threshold to govern the home's heating and cooling system. In most cases, thermostats can also be programmed with different target temperatures in order to keep energy usage at a minimum during the hours when you're least likely to benefit from the heating and cooling.

At the most basic level, home automation extends that scheduled programmability to lighting, so that you can suit your energy usage to your usual daily schedule. With more flexible home automation systems, electrical outlets or even individual devices can also be automatically powered down during hours of the day when they're not needed. As with isolated devices like thermostats and sprinkler systems, the scheduling can be further broken down to distinguish between weekends and even seasons of the year, in some cases.

Set schedules are helpful, but many of us keep different hours from day to day. Energy costs can be even further reduced by programming "macros" into the system and controlling it remotely whenever needed. In other words, you could set up a "coming home" event that turns on lights and heating as you're driving home after work, for example, and activate it all with one tap on your smartphone. An opposite "leaving home" event could save you

from wasting energy on forgotten lights and appliances once you've left for the day. The system has been designed for measurement of electrical parameters of household appliances. Important functions to the system are the case of modeling, setup, and use. From the consumer point of view, electrical power consumption of various appliances in a house along with supply voltage and current is key parameter. The measurement of electrical parameters of home appliances is done by interfacing with fabricated sensing modules. The details of the design and development of the sensing modules are provided in the following sections

4. BLOCK DIAGRAM

AT MEGA 328

The Atmel 8-bit AVR RISC-based microcontroller combines 32 KB ISP flash memory with read-while-write capabilities, 1 KB EEPROM, 2 KBSRAM, 23 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, three flexible timer/counters with compare modes, internal and external interrupts, serial programmable USART, a byte-oriented 2-wire serial interface, SPI serial port, 6-channel 10-bit A/D converter (8-channels in TQFP and QFN/MLF packages), programmable watchdog timer with internal oscillator, and five software selectable power saving modes. The device operates between 1.8-5.5 volts. The device achieves throughput approaching 1 MIPS per MHz

LM 7805

LM7805 PINOUT DIAGRAM

The LM7805, like most other regulators, is a three-pin IC.

Pin 1 (Input Pin): The Input pin is the pin that accepts the incoming DC voltage, which the voltage regulator will eventually regulate down to 5 volts.

Pin 2 (Ground): Ground pin establishes the ground for the regulator.

Pin 3 (Output Pin): The Output pin is the regulated 5 volts DC.

PIR SENSOR

A passive infrared sensor (PIR sensor) is an electronic sensor that measures infrared (IR) light radiating from objects in its field of view. They are most often used in PIR-based motion detectors. All objects with a temperature above absolute zero emit heat energy in the form of radiation. Usually this radiation is invisible to the human eye because it radiates at infrared wavelengths, but it can be detected by electronic devices designed for such a purpose. The term *passive* in this instance refers to the fact that PIR devices do not generate or radiate any energy for detection purposes. They work entirely by detecting the energy given off by other objects. PIR sensors don't detect or measure "heat"; instead they detect the infrared radiation emitted or reflected from an object.

. An individual PIR sensor detects changes in the amount of infrared radiation impinging upon it, which varies depending on the temperature and surface characteristics of the objects in front of the sensor. When an object, such as a human, passes in front of the background, such as a wall, the temperature at that point in the sensor's field of view will rise from room temperature to body temperature, and then back again. The sensor converts the resulting change in the incoming infrared radiation into a change in the output voltage, and this triggers the detection. Moving objects of similar temperature to the background but different surface characteristics may also have a different infrared emission pattern, and thus sometimes trigger the detector.

PIRs come in many configurations for a wide variety of applications. The most common models have numerous or mirror segments, an effective range of about ten metres (thirty feet), and a field of view less than 180 degrees. Models with wider fields of view, including 360 degrees, are available—typically designed to mount on a ceiling. Some larger PIRs are made with single segment mirrors and can sense changes in infrared energy over one hundred feet away from the PIR. There are also PIRs designed with reversible orientation mirrors which allow either broad coverage (110° wide) or very narrow "curtain" coverage, or with individually selectable segments to "shape" the coverage.

PIR sensors allow you to sense motion, almost always used to detect whether a human has moved in or out of the sensor's range. They are small, inexpensive, low-power, easy to use and don't wear out. For that reason they are commonly found in appliances and gadgets used in homes or businesses. They are often referred to as PIRs.

PIRs are basically made of a pyroelectric sensor which can detect levels of infrared radiation. Everything emits some low level radiation, and the hotter something is, the more radiation is emitted. The sensor in a motion detector is actually split in two halves. The reason for that is that we are looking to detect motion (change) not average IR levels. The two halves are wired up so that they cancel each other out. If one half sees more or less IR radiation than the other, the output will swing high or low.

Along with the pyro electric sensor is a bunch of supporting circuitry, resistors and capacitors. This chip takes the output of the sensor and does some minor processing on it to emit a digital output pulse from the analog sensor. For many basic projects or products that need to detect when a person has left or entered the area, or has approached, PIR sensors are great. They are low power and low cost, pretty rugged, have a wide lens range, and are easy to interface with. Note that PIRs won't tell you how many people are around or how close they are to the sensor, the lens is often fixed to a certain sweep and distance and they are also sometimes set off by house pets.

PIR sensors allow you to sense motion, almost always used to detect whether a human has moved in or out of the sensor's range. They are small, inexpensive, low-power, easy to use and don't wear out. For that reason they are commonly found in appliances and gadgets used in homes or businesses. PIRs are basically made of a pyroelectric sensor, which can detect levels of infrared radiation. Everything emits some low level radiation, and the hotter something is, the more radiation is emitted. The sensor in a motion detector is actually split in two halves. The reason for that is that we are looking to detect motion (change) not average IR levels. The two halves are wired up

so that they cancel each other out. If one half sees more or less IR radiation than the other, the output will swing high or low.

REAL TIME CLOCK

A Real Time Clock (RTC) is basically just like a watch - it runs on a battery and keeps time for you even when there is a power outage. Using an RTC, you can keep track of long timelines, even if you reprogram your microcontroller or a power plug.

The real time clock (RTC) is widely used device that provides accurate time and date for many applications. Many systems such as IBM pc come with RTC chip on mother board. RTC chip uses an internal battery which keeps time and date even when the power is off. In some microcontrollers have inbuilt RTC while others requires interfacing. Most widely used RTC chip is DS1307 from Dallas Semiconductor. It uses external lithium battery of 3V to keep operating for over maximum 10 years in the absence of external power supply. DS1307 uses CMOS technology to keep power consumption low. According to datasheet of DS1307 from Dallas, it keeps track of “Seconds, Minutes, and Hours, Day of week, Date, Month and Year”.

RELAY

A relay is an electrically operated switch. Many relays use an electromagnet to mechanically operate a switch, but other operating principles are also used, such as solid-state relays. Relays are used where it is necessary to control a circuit by a low-power signal (with complete electrical isolation between control and controlled circuits), or where several circuits must be controlled by one signal. The first relays were used in long distance telegraph circuits as

amplifiers: they repeated the signal coming in from one circuit and re-transmitted it on another circuit. Relays were used extensively in telephone exchanges and early computers to perform logical operations.

A type of relay that can handle the high power required to directly control an electric motor or other loads is called a contactor. Solid-state relays control power circuits with no moving parts, instead using a semiconductor device to perform switching. Relays with calibrated operating characteristics and sometimes multiple operating coils are used to protect electrical circuits from overload or faults; in modern electric power systems these functions are performed by digital instruments still called "protective relays".

A simple electromagnetic relay consists of a coil of wire wrapped around a soft iron core, an iron yoke which provides a low reluctance path for magnetic flux, a movable iron armature, and one or more sets of contacts (there are two in the relay pictured). The armature is hinged to the yoke and mechanically linked to one or more sets of moving contacts. It is held in place by a spring so that when the relay is de-energized there is an air gap in the magnetic circuit. In this condition, one of the two sets of contacts in the relay pictured is closed, and the other set is open. Other relays may have more or fewer sets of contacts depending on their function. The relay in the picture also has a wire connecting the armature to the yoke. This ensures continuity of the circuit between the moving contacts on the armature, and the circuit track on the printed circuit board (PCB) via the yoke, which is soldered to the PCB.

When an electric current is passed through the coil it generates a magnetic field that activates the armature, and the consequent movement of the movable contact(s) either makes or breaks (depending upon construction) a connection with a fixed contact. If the set of contacts was closed when the relay was de-energized, then the movement opens the contacts and breaks the connection, and vice versa if the contacts were open. When the current to the coil is switched off, the armature is returned by a force, approximately half as strong as the magnetic force, to its relaxed position. Usually this force is provided by a spring, but gravity is also used commonly in industrial motor starters. Most relays are manufactured to operate quickly. In a low-voltage application this reduces noise; in a high voltage or current application it reduces arcing.

When the coil is energized with direct current, a diode is often placed across the coil to dissipate the energy from the collapsing magnetic field at deactivation, which would otherwise generate a voltage spike dangerous to semiconductor circuit components. Some automotive relays include a diode inside the relay case. Alternatively, a contact protection network consisting of a capacitor and resistor in series (snubber circuit) may absorb the surge. If the coil is designed to be energized with alternating current (AC), a small copper "shading ring" can be crimped to the end of the solenoid, creating a small out-of-phase current which increases the minimum pull on the armature during the AC cycle.^[1]

Relays are used wherever it is necessary to control a high power or high voltage circuit with a low power circuit. The first application of relays was in long telegraph systems, where the weak signal received at an intermediate station could control a contact, regenerating the signal for further transmission. High-voltage or high-current devices can be controlled with small, low voltage wiring and pilots switches. Operators can be isolated from the high voltage circuit. Low power devices such as microprocessors can drive relays to control electrical loads beyond their direct drive capability. In an automobile, a starter relay allows the high current of the cranking motor to be controlled with small wiring and contacts in the ignition key.

LCD

LCD uses a liquid crystal to produce a visible image. Liquid crystal displays are super-thin technology display screen that are generally used in laptop computer screen, TVs, cell phones and portable video games. LCD's technologies allow displays to be much thinner when compared to cathode ray tube (CRT) technology.

GSM MODULE

One of the most important conclusions from the early tests of the new GSM technology was that the new standard should employ Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) technology. This ensured the support of major corporate players like Nokia, Ericsson and Siemens, and the flexibility of having access to a broad range of suppliers and the potential to get product faster into the marketplace. After a series of tests, the GSM digital standard was proven to work in 1988. With global coverage goals in mind, being compatible with GSM from day one is a prerequisite for any new system that would add functionality to GSM. As with other 2G systems, GSM handles voice efficiently, but the support for data and Internet applications is limited. A data connection is established in just the same way as for a regular voice call; the user dials in and a circuit-switched connection continues during the entire session. If the user disconnects and wants to re-connect, the dial-in sequence has to be repeated. This issue, coupled with the limitation that users are billed for the time that they are connected, creates a need for packet data for GSM. The digital nature of GSM allows the transmission of data (both synchronous and asynchronous) to or from ISDN terminals, although the most basic service support by GSM is telephony.¹⁷ Speech, which is inherently analog, has to be digitized. The method employed by ISDN, and by current telephone systems for multiplexing voice lines over high-speed trunks and optical fiber lines, is Pulse Coded Modulation (PCM).

GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) is a standard developed by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) to describe protocols for second-generation (2G) digital cellular networks used by mobile phones. 2G networks developed as a replacement for first generation (1G) analog cellular networks, and the GSM standard originally described a digital, circuit-switched network optimized for full duplex voice telephony. This expanded over time to include data communications, first by circuit-switched transport, then by packet data transport via GPRS (General Packet Radio Services) and EDGE (Enhanced Data rates for GSM Evolution or EGPRS).

Subsequently, the 3GPP developed third-generation (3G) UMTS standards followed by fourth-generation (4G) LTE Advanced standards, which do not form part of the ETSI GSM standard.

GSM is a cellular network, which means that cell phones connect to it by searching for cells in the immediate vicinity. There are five different cell sizes in a GSM network—macro, micro, pico, femto, and umbrella cells. The coverage area of each cell varies according to the implementation environment. Macro cells can be regarded as cells

produce a highly accurate temperature sensor.

The integrated circuit has many transistors in it -- two in the middle, some in each amplifier, some in the constant current source, and some in the curvature compensation circuit. All of that is fit into the tiny package with three leads.

SERVOMOTOR

Servo motors have been around for a long time and are utilized in many applications. They are small in size but pack a big punch and are very energy-efficient. These features allow them to be used to operate remote-controlled or radio-controlled toy cars, robots and airplanes. Servo motors are also used in industrial applications, robotics, in-line manufacturing, pharmaceuticals and food services. But how will it work?

The servo circuitry is built right inside the motor unit and has a positionable shaft, which usually is fitted with a gear (as shown below). The motor is controlled with an electric signal which determines the amount of movement of the shaft. To fully understand how the servo works, you need to take a look under the hood. Inside there is a pretty simple set-up: a small dc motor, potentiometer, and a control circuit. The motor is attached by gears to the control wheel. When the shaft of the motor is at the desired position, power supplied to the motor is stopped. If not, the motor is turned in the appropriate direction. The desired position is sent via electrical pulses through the signal wire. The motor's speed is proportional to the difference between its actual position and desired position. So if the motor is near the desired position, it will turn slowly, otherwise it will turn fast. This is called proportional control. This means the motor will only run as hard as necessary to accomplish the task at hand, a very efficient little guy. Servos are controlled by sending an electrical pulse of variable width, or pulse width modulation (PWM), through the control wire. There is a minimum pulse, a maximum pulse, and a repetition rate. A servo motor can usually only turn 90 degrees in either direction for a total of 180 degree movement. The motor's neutral position is defined as the position where the servo has the same amount of potential rotation in the both the clockwise or counter-clockwise direction. The PWM sent to the motor determines position of the shaft, and based on the duration of the pulse sent via the control wire; the rotor will turn to the desired position. The servo motor expects to see a pulse every 20 milliseconds (ms) and the length of the pulse will determine how far the motor turns. For example, a

1.5ms pulse will make the motor turn to the 90-degree position. Shorter than 1.5ms moves it to 0 degrees, and any longer than 1.5ms will turn the servo to 180 degrees.

There are two types of servo motors - AC and DC. AC servo can handle higher current surges and tend to be used in industrial machinery. DC servos are not designed for high current surges and are usually better suited for smaller applications. Generally speaking, DC motors are less expensive than their AC counterparts. These are also servo motors that have been built specifically for continuous rotation, making it an easy way to get your robot moving. They feature two ball bearings on the output shaft for reduced friction and easy access to the rest-point adjustment potentiometer. Servos are used in radio-controlled airplanes to position control surfaces like elevators, rudders, walking a robot, or operating grippers. Servo motors are small, have built-in control circuitry and have good power for their size.

In food services and pharmaceuticals, the tools are designed to be used in harsher environments, where the potential for corrosion is high due to being washed at high pressures and temperatures repeatedly to maintain strict hygiene standards. Servos are also used in in-line manufacturing, where high repetition yet precise work is necessary

4. WORKING OF AUTOMATED SMART ROOMS

Home automation systems work by managing the electric power of the equipment being automatically controlled. The degree of 'intelligence' and how it is distributed between the elements of the home automation system varies with the design and manufacturer.

Control can be implemented by isolated sensors, timers and processors embedded in the switches and relays. Centralised control can be obtained through networked sensors linked to a controller or computer which then operates the power systems of equipment throughout the house.

The operation of more sophisticated equipment such as central heaters, air conditioners or home theatres can also be brought under the control of the automation system, but with more intelligent controlled devices. Take care to ensure the controller's instructions do not create conflicts, e.g. heating areas that are cooled by the air conditioner.

Automation equipment potentially includes any appliance or machinery in the home whose operation is controlled through its electricity supply, for example:

- hot water system

- appliances
- home entertainment, home office and other electronic equipment
- lighting
- heating and cooling/air conditioning systems
- fans and air pumps/heat shifters
- powered window blinds, shutters and awnings
- powered vents and window openings
- water pumps, pool pumps and spas
- garage doors
- security systems.

Motion sensors, light sensors and temperature sensors can be integrated into the automation system.

The home and its lighting, appliances and systems can be controlled by:

- on-site controllers, which may be special proprietary devices, often activated by touchscreens, or tablets/computers
- remote controllers, allowing equipment to be controlled outside the home or at a distance in the home often by smart phones or tablets
- sensors that operate home equipment in response to changes in the home environment, such as the presence of occupants or changes in external temperature.

A wide variety of automation systems is available and most require a professional to design and install. Complete packages from manufacturers offer the hardware and software for central and remote control. Some suppliers promote a more do-it-yourself experience using wireless communications to connect the controllers and sensors, but almost all systems require a registered electrical contractor to install the equipment. Wireless systems are more suited for installation in existing houses, as they do not require a control wire to be used for each switch or sensor. Some systems use the power cabling to send the control signals.

5. CONCLUSION

A smart power monitoring and control system has been designed and developed toward the implementation of automated smart rooms. The developed system effectively monitors and controls the electrical appliances usage. The sensor networks are programmed with various user interfaces suitable for users of varying ability and for expert users such that the system can be maintained easily and interacted simply. Automated smart rooms can be the real future because of the service that it is providing .it can be energy savior for the future. This study also aims to assess consumer’s response toward perceptions of smart grid technologies, their advantages and disadvantages, possible concerns, and overall perceived utility.

6. REFERENCE

1. X. P. Liu, W. Gueaieb, S. C. Mukhopadhyay, W. Warwick, and Z. Yin, "Guest editorial introduction to the focused section on wireless mechatronics." *IEEE IASME TRANS. Mechatronics*, vol.17, no.3, pp. 397-403' Jun. 2012.

2. N. van de m EUGHEUVEL, a. Pandharipande, D. Caicedo, and P . P. J. van den Hof,” *Distributed lighting control with daylight and occupancy adaptation*”, *Energy buildings* , vol. 75 ,pp. 321-329, Jun. 2014.
3. I. Koutsopoulos and L. Tassiulas, “*Optimal control policies for power demand scheduling in the smart grid*, “ *IEEE J. sel. Areas Commun.*, vol.30, no. 6,pp. 1049-1060, Jul. 2012.
4. Z. Li-ming, L. Bao-cheng, T. Qing-hau, and W. Li-ping,”*The development and technological research of intelligent electrical building*,” in *Proc. China Int. Conf. Elect. Distrib.*, Sep. 2014, pp. 88-92